

Spatiotemporal variation in hatching success and nestling sex ratios track rapid movement of a songbird hybrid zone

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Supplementary figure 1. Species identity of both parents influenced the proportion of eggs hatched at Hawk Mountain. Hatching success increased with both (a) male and (b) female genotypic indices, which ranged from 0 for hybrids to 0.5 for non-hybrid individuals (BCCH or CACH). Lines denote model predictions \pm 95% CI. Data points represent individual breeders; point sizes increase with number of individuals.

Supplementary figure 2. Compatibility index, a measure of the proportion of homozygous loci within breeding pairs, did not predict proportion of male nestlings at Hawk Mountain. Lines denote model predictions \pm 95% CI. Data points represent individual pairs; point sizes increase with number of pairs.

Supplementary figure 3. Clutch size did not influence hatching success. Lines denote model predictions \pm 95% CI, combining data from all four study sites and all sampled years. Points represent individual nests; point sizes increase with number of nests.

Supplementary figure 4. Clutch initiation date, measured as day of the year, did not influence hatching success. Lines denote model predictions \pm 95% CI, combining data from all four study sites and all sampled years. Data points represent individual clutches; point sizes increase with number of clutches.

Supplementary figure 5. Proportion of male nestlings within broods did not vary with hatching success at Hawk Mountain. Lines denote model predictions \pm 95% CI. Data points represent individual broods; point sizes increase with number of broods.

Supplementary figure 6. Clutch size did not vary with pair genotypic index at Hawk Mountain. Lines denote model predictions \pm 95% CI. Data points represent individual pairs; point sizes increase with number of pairs.